

OHSCR: Benchmarks Dataset for Offline Handwritten Sindhi Character Recognition

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Abstract

This research work presents a unique dataset for offline handwritten Sindhi character recognition. It has 7800 character images in total, divided into multiple categories by 150 writers of various ages, genders, and professional backgrounds. Each writer writes the 52 Sindhi characters in the designed form. With a high-quality scanner, all of the written samples were scanned. After that, all the handwritten Sindhi characters were cropped from the collected designed form, and the cropped images were saved in '.png' format. For the benefit of the Sindhi research community, this work suggests an image dataset for character recognition in handwritten Sindhi. The dataset will be made publically available. For the Sindhi language, this dataset can be used to create and test handwritten character recognition systems and provide helpful insights through writer identification. The dataset has been divided into the training set and the test set, with 80% for training and 20% for testing. The different preprocessing techniques used to remove noise from scanned images to create a clean dataset. The dataset created as a result of this research is the world's first openly accessible dataset for handwritten research, and it can be useful for writer identification systems and handwriting recognition systems.

Index Terms: Benchmark Dataset, Handwritten Character Recognition, Machine Learning, Pattern Recognition, Sindhi Language.

I. INTRODUCTION

Handwritten Character Recognition (HCR) is a technique of detection of characters from images, documents, and other different sources. In the field of machine learning, pattern recognition, and image processing it is an extremely difficult and complicated research area due to variability of human writing. A computer can read and interpret handwritten text from different sources like; documents, images, touch displays, and other gadgets [1]. In general, HCR is majorly classified into two distinct categories, i.e., 'Offline' and 'Online' handwritten character recognition. Online handwritten character recognition refers to real-time recognition. In online frameworks, characters are recognized as they are composed. Here a concept of digital ink is utilized, and the sensor is used to analyze pen write tip movements. The offline handwritten character recognition includes the automatic conversion of text to machine code which can be utilized inside computer and text processing applications. In other words, we can say that it deals with scanned handwritten documents [2], and [3].

There are two primary types of offline handwritten character recognition. The first one is "Machine-Printed Characters" and the second one is "Handwritten Characters". Handwritten characters can be formed of several different styles and sizes by different writers or by the same writer and the machine-printed characters are

identical in pitch, position, and size for any particular text style [4]. Hence, machine-printed characters are much simpler to recognize as compared to handwritten characters. Compared to online handwritten character recognition, offline handwritten character recognition is more challenging because different people have diverse writing styles, speeds of writing, size, and overlap of letters [5], and [6].

In the past few decades, numerous analysts have investigated and created different HCR systems for different languages like Arabic, Japanese, Russian, Chinese, Bangla, Urdu, Devanagari, English, and so on. Currently, the Sindhi language character recognition system is just getting started, and inadequate research has been noted in this domain [7], and [8]. We need to recognize the characters, words, and sentences in several areas. There are numerous distinctive sorts of applications where we are required to recognize offline handwritten Sindhi characters. These applications are; Language identification, Bank cheque reading, postal addresses, form processing, signature verification, and many other related tasks.

In today's world, typed Sindhi characters can be effectively and accurately recognized by the computer but Sindhi handwritten characters are difficult to recognize by machine because Sindhi script is a cursive script [7], and [8]. In other languages, numerous investigations have been done to recognize these characters and numerous

calculations have been proposed to recognize handwritten characters. A standard dataset of the Sindhi handwritten images is required and necessary to design any recognition system. The offline handwritten Sindhi recognition system lacks the standard dataset. In this study, we proposed an image dataset for the Offline Handwritten Sindhi Character Recognition (OHSCR). The development of a publicly accessible dataset is important to assist the over 60 million Sindhi language speakers. This research paper addresses this gap as well as incorporates additional features that are common to many standard handwriting datasets and makes it publicly available to researchers as a benchmark dataset for handwriting recognition studies.

This paper's main contributions are as follows:

1. For the offline handwritten Sindhi character recognition system, we provide a benchmark dataset called "OHSCR".
2. As there is no complete Sindhi HCR system, there is a need for a complete Sindhi HCR system that recognizes unlimited characters, words, and sentences for the Sindhi script.

The following sections of this research work are structured as follows. Section II - Literary Work, shows the several datasets that have been developed for other languages, Section III - Methodology, shows the process of creating the dataset, Section IV - Results, outlines the experiments and discussions and finally, Section V - Conclusion, summarizes finding and suggests directions for future research.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

With a focus on handwriting datasets, this section discusses related research that has been done in the area of Handwritten Recognition (HWR). Early in the 20th century, machine learning and pattern recognition researchers began to focus significantly on handwritten text recognition, which prompted the creation of datasets. Many studies on the English, European, Arabic, and Chinese languages have been done. However, research on the Sindhi language is a matter of concern. The requirement for a benchmark dataset is one common issue in the research. Many document-processing research groups have gathered large character and numeric datasets and made them available to other researchers worldwide in order to enable results on the standardized dataset. However, these datasets already in existence are accessible in many different languages, including English, Bangla, Urdu, Japanese, Chinese, Arabic, and Devanagari [7], and [8]. One of the most popular datasets for English sentences used for Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) is IAM-OnDB [9]. In this dataset, English handwritten samples that gathered online and offline. To the online version of the IAM-OnDB dataset, 221 authors in total contributed. It includes 1700 digitized forms that are identified at the word level and contain 86,272-segmented words. There are 1539 digitized forms in the offline IAM-OnDB. In the offline version of the IAM-OnDB dataset, the labeling at the words and sentence level is available. It contains 5685 sentences and 115,320 words contributed by 657 participants. The data is saved in XML file format and can be viewed as 'tif images'.

The NIST released the very first dataset for handwritten character and digit recognition in 1995 [10], and [11]. NIST adopted an offline approach to collect data from writers and since then has released updated and improved versions of its datasets. The most recent version is SD-19. It is also called NIST Special Database-19. It developed with the help of 3600 volunteers. It has about 800,000 separate characters and numerals. In 1998 NIST joined two datasets "SD-1" and "SD-3" to form the dataset called MNIST. It collects handwriting data offline and makes available 70,000 isolated digits at no cost [11]. Different machine learning and digit recognition systems have made significant use of this dataset. There are 60,000 training images and 10,000 testing images in this dataset. The Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR) dataset was created in 1994 by the CEDAR. The main goal of CEDAR is to recognize the addresses written on envelopes in order to automate postal operations [12], and [13]. It obtained information in an offline mode. A total of 21,179 scanned forms, 10,570 segmented words, and 27,835 isolated characters were gathered from 1500 participants [14]. This database has been used to test different techniques such as handwriting segmentation, cursive digit recognition, character recognition, and word segmentation. IRONOFF is a dual on/off dataset developed by Ecole Polytechnique, University of Nantes (France). It contains data samples in both English and French, handwritten by 700 different individuals [15]. It contains 32,000-character images and 50,000 segmented words. It may be used to recognize handwritten text both online and offline. In 2013, Qatar University released its first dataset called QUWI. It contains Arabic handwritten and English handwritten samples [16]. This dataset has word-by-word labeling. In total, 1017 volunteers participated in the compilation of 5085 documents in QUWI. A total of 100,000 words were retrieved from these documents, which were scanned at 600 dpi.

In the year 2000, Hand-printed Chinese Character "HCL2000" [17] and Handwritten Geek "GRUHD" [18] datasets were released. A complete set of GB2312-80 first-level Chinese characters, accurately written inside a preprinted character box, must be obtained from HCL2000 writers. The GRUHD dataset was divided into two subsets: the first contained hand-printed Greek letters and numbers, while the second had infinite Greek poetry that could be used to evaluate text-line segmentation. OHASD is an online Arabic handwritten dataset [19]. A total of 48 authors and 154 paragraphs are in this collection. It is 19,467 characters long and 3,825 words long. Among other things, the dataset is used in word segmentation, line extraction, annotation, and word retrieval systems. An offline database called CENPARMI was used to identify Arabic handwriting. It was written by 228 participants from Saudi Arabia and 100 people from Canada and consists of single numbers, letters, strings, and words. Arabic characters, numbers, and wordmarks have all been recognized using the dataset [20]. Following our prior discussions regarding a variety of datasets across different contexts, we now provide a comparative overview of these databases in Table I, emphasizing their individual strengths and weaknesses.

Table I: Comparative Overview of Existing Datasets

Database	Strengths	Weaknesses	Year	Writers	Mode	Language	Availability
IAM-OnDB [9]	Multimodal	Small Dataset Size	2005	657	Offline	English	Public
NIST [10][11]	Large Dataset Size and Variety of Writing Styles.	Isolated Digits	1995	3600	Offline	English	Proprietary
MNIST [11]	Widely used Benchmark.	Limited to Digits Only	1998	-	Offline	English	Public
CEDAR [12] [13] [14]	Large Dataset Size and Multilingual	It Contains Isolated Characters and Words	1994	1500	Offline	English	Proprietary
IRONOFF [15]	Diverse Range Of Writing Styles and Variations.	It Contains Isolated Handwritten Text Samples.	1999	700	Offline /Online	French	Proprietary
QUWI [16]	Large and Diverse Set of Handwritten Arabic Text.	It Contains only Sentences.	2013	1017	Offline	Arabic	Public
HCL2000 [17]	Variety of Writing Styles.	Small Dataset Size	2009	1000	Offline	Chinese	Proprietary
GRUHD [18]	Different Handwriting Styles.	Limited Amount of Data	2001	1000	Offline	Greek	Proprietary
OHASD [19]	Variety of Writing Styles.	Small Dataset Size	2000	48	Offline /Online	Arabic	Public
CENPARMI [20]	Diverse Range of Writing Styles and Variations.	Limited Amount of Data	2008	328	Offline	Arabic	Proprietary

From the related work study, it has been observed that standard datasets provide a framework for performing cutting-edge character recognition research, including features such as writer identification. The Handwritten Character Recognition (HCR) system has been enhanced and enriched in most languages of the world [21]. There is no publicly and freely available Sindhi language dataset with which to train recognition systems.

A. Sindhi Language Writing

The Sindhi language is an ancient Indus Valley language with having hundred-year-old history. The title has been derived from Sindhu, the old name of the river Indus. The Sindhi language is broadly spoken in the Sindh province of Pakistan. Approximately 60 million people speak Sindhi in Pakistan, various states of India as well as other different areas of the world. Most languages are enhanced and enriched with their Handwritten Character Recognition (HCR) system but in the Sindhi language, little work has been done. The development of an HCR system is easy for some languages, such as Latin script and some other non-cursive languages, but it might be difficult for languages that are cursive or have a larger character set, like Sindhi. The Sindhi language contains 52 characters, while the equivalent numbers in Persian, Arabic, and Urdu are 32, 28, and 38 respectively [8]. Sindhi Script is a cursive script that has a large number of characters. There are various issues and challenges, which make the recognition of HCR a challenging task and influence the recognition rate to a significant extent.

The issues and challenges are:

- Different writing styles of different writers.
- Variations in font size and pen ink.
- A significant character count.
- A larger amount of dots and their alignment in characters.
- Characters differ in dot counts, places, and orientations but have the same basic shape.
- The lack, of clarity between the characters with a slight distinction.

- Cursive-ness and Unicode representation
- Context-sensitive shapes, ligatures, skewness, and noise.

Sindhi writing differs from other languages in its style. The writing system for Sindhi is right to left; a word might contain a character at the beginning, middle, or end. The joining of letters shows the cursive nature of language and many Sindhi characters have several dots and different placement and orientations of dots. A unique number of dots at a unique point distinguishes some character shapes, which possess the same basis. In figure I, if a single extra dot is added to the second character پ (Bay Badak) it will become the third character پ (Bay Bok).

7	6	5	4	3	2	1
ت	ت	ت	پ	پ	ب	ا
14	13	12	11	10	9	8
ج	جم	ج	ج	پ	ث	ت
21	20	19	18	17	16	15
ڙ	ڙ	د	خ	ع	ج	ج
28	27	26	25	24	23	22
س	ز	ز	ر	ذ	ڀ	ڀ
35	34	33	32	31	30	29
غ	ع	ظ	ط	نھن	س	ش
42	41	40	39	38	37	36
ڳ	گ	س	ک	ق	ق	ف
49	48	47	46	45	44	43
و	ن	ن	م	ل	سٿي	گھ
		52	51	50		
		ڀي	ء	ھ		

Figure I: Handwritten Sindhi 52 Characters

In the same way, if an extra dot is added to the fifth character ت (Tay Taro) it will become the seventh and

eighth characters ٹ, ٺ (Tay Topi, Say Sawab). The process of offline handwritten character recognition remains extremely challenging and requires a high degree of precision. Therefore, there is a need to examine the challenges and difficulties posed by the Sindhi script for the development of offline HCR systems. The goal of creating this dataset is to provide it as a benchmark dataset for handwriting recognition research, freely accessible to the scientific community. Figure I shows the 52 handwritten Sindhi characters' samples.

III. OHSCR METHOD

Our contribution is to propose a new dataset called "OHSCR" for Offline handwritten Sindhi character recognition systems. Figure II shows a proposed diagram for Offline Handwritten Sindhi Characters.

Figure II: Proposed Diagram of OHSCR System

The steps of the Algorithm are as follows:

- **Step-1:** Distribute the designed OHSCR form among people to collect handwritten samples.
- **Step-2:** Scan the collected form samples with the help of a scanner.
- **Step-3:** Crop each character from the scanned OHSCR form.
- **Step-4:** Apply preprocessing techniques to improve image quality.
- **Step-5:** Save pre-processed images into the database folder.

IV. RESULTS

A. Data Collection

The primary goal is to collect image samples of different writers' handwritten Sindhi characters. As a result, a form is created to accomplish this. Figure III shows the form for OHSCR. The form is made up of 52 alphabets, each of which has been printed, as well as 52 blank blocks. Each letter was to be written in empty blocks by the writers. There are 150 writers in all.

The form has been distributed among different people from different departments, including the police, health, and

education departments, as well as high school and university students.

Form for OHSCR							
Name: _____		Age: _____		Designation: _____			
ا	1	چ	14	ز	27	ک	40
ب	2	چ	15	س	28	گ	41
پ	3	چ	16	ش	29	گ	42
پ	4	ح	17	ص	30	گھ	43
ن	5	خ	18	ض	31	گ	44
ٹ	6	د	19	ط	32	ل	45
ٹ	7	ڈ	20	ظ	33	م	46
ن	8	ڈ	21	ع	34	ن	47
ٹ	9	ب	22	غ	35	ٹ	48
پ	10	پ	23	ف	36	و	49
ج	11	ن	24	قا	37	ھ	50
چ	12	ر	25	ق	38	ء	51
چھ	13	ڑ	26	ک	39	ي	52

Figure III: Sample form for OHSCR

During the collection of data, handwritten samples were collected from different people of different age groups. Each person has written 52 characters from the first letter ا (Alef Akh) to the last letter ي (Yeh Yakoo). The samples were collected from 150 different people belonging to different age groups. The age groups formed into four groups. Group-A contains persons aged from 10-20 years, Group-B contains persons aged from 21-40 years, Group-C contains persons aged from 41-60 years, and Group-D contains persons aged from 61-70 years respectively. Figure IV shows the age distribution of different writers.

Figure IV: Age Groups of Different Writers

We have collected 150 samples of each character, which means we have collected 150 characters of the first letter ا (Alef Akh), 150 characters of the second letter پ (Bay Badak) up to the last letter ي (Yeh Yakoo). All the

collected samples were written on white paper designed to form and there were no restrictions on ink color, line thickness, character sequence, or pen types, such as ball pen or ink/gel pen. Figure V shows the form sample filled by the writer. The dataset's diversity was maintained by selecting writers with a variety of professional and educational backgrounds, as well as age and gender. Only 15% of the 150 writers who have contributed thus far are left-handed, with the remaining 85% being right-handed.

Form for OHSOCR

Name: Muhammad Ali Age: 25 Designation: Student

ا	ا	14	ج	ج	27	ز	ز	40	ک	ک	1
ب	ب	15	چ	چ	28	س	س	41	گ	گ	2
پ	پ	16	جھ	جھ	29	ش	ش	42	ڳ	ڳ	3
پھ	پھ	17	ح	ح	30	ھ	ھ	43	گھ	گھ	4
ت	ت	18	خ	خ	31	نھ	نھ	44	گھ	گھ	5
تھ	تھ	19	د	د	32	ط	ط	45	ل	ل	6
تھ	تھ	20	ڌ	ڌ	33	ظ	ظ	46	م	م	7
ن	ن	21	ڌ	ڌ	34	ع	ع	47	ن	ن	8
نھ	نھ	22	ڍ	ڍ	35	غ	غ	48	ڻ	ڻ	9
پ	پ	23	ڍ	ڍ	36	ف	ف	49	و	و	10
ج	ج	24	ڏ	ڏ	37	ڦ	ڦ	50	ھ	ھ	11
جھ	جھ	25	ر	ر	38	ق	ق	51	ء	ء	12
جھ	جھ	26	ڙ	ڙ	39	ڪ	ڪ	52	ي	ي	13

Figure V: Handwritten Sample of Sindhi Characters Filled by Writer

B. Data Preparation

After collecting the handwritten samples written by different writers, an ‘HP Scanjet 200 flatbed scanner’ was used to scan written white pages at 600 dpi. Since the paper was white, all of the letters were written with black and blue pens. Each written piece of white paper went through a challenging cropping process, where each character was cropped separately with the ‘Microsoft Paint’ program, in order to extract the characters.

The images were stored in PNG format. Separating isolated symbols from a scanned image is a time-consuming procedure. Figure VI shows an example set of cropped characters taken from a white piece of paper.

Figure VI: Dataset of Sindhi Handwritten Characters with some Image Samples

During the cropping process, every written letter was cropped and saved in a separate folder. Every letter's images were saved with the same resolution because each letter was written 150 times by 150 writers, and each letter had 150 images. Training and testing are the two main folders in the dataset. Each folder has 52 folders containing cropped images of each letter, with the training folder containing 80% of the images and the testing folder containing 20%.

C. Preprocessing

Preprocessing is a technique used to remove low-frequency background noise. This technique is mostly done to improve an image's quality and characteristics in preparation for additional processing. To enhance the quality of images a pre-processing method was applied to each collected handwritten sample form. First, all similar letters are grouped in a folder, resulting in 52 folders. Each folder is read independently, with each image in the folder being scaled and normalized, as illustrated in figure VII where related letters are grouped and written.

Figure VII: Similar Letters Group ‘Yakoo’

In a handwritten character recognition system, various preprocessing steps can be carried out on the image. The preprocessing steps are as follows:

1) Transformation of RGB Images to Grayscale Images:

In the preprocessing first, we resized the images because when we crop the characters from the scanned paper we saved the cropped character images with different image sizes. With the help of the ‘imresize’ method, we have resized every image. In our dataset, every image is 128x128 in size. After that, we transformed the RGB images into a grayscale image. The ‘rgb2gray’ method is used to convert RGB images into grayscale images.

Figure VIII: Transformation of RGB to Grayscale

Figure VIII illustrates the conversion of an RGB image to a grayscale image. This formula calculates the grayscale

intensity for each pixel by taking a weighted sum of its RGB values. The weights (0.2126, 0.7152, and 0.0722) are chosen based on the sensitivity of the human eye to different colors [22].

The formula used in the “rgb2gray” method, often referred to as the luminosity method, as can be seen in eq. (1):

$$Y = 0.2126 \cdot R + 0.7152 \cdot G + 0.0722 \cdot B \quad (1)$$

Where:

R, G, and B are the red, green, and blue values of the pixel respectively and Y is the resulting grayscale intensity.

2) Transformation of Grayscale Images to Binary Images:

Image binarization is the basic and important step in the HCR system. The result of character recognition depends upon binarization because the highly binarized image can give more accuracy to the character recognition system. In the grayscale image, there are 256 combinations of black color and white color. With the help of the "im2bw" method, we have transformed a grayscale image into a bi-level or binary image. The image is transformed into a bi-level image by determining whether the value of each pixel exceeds 255. The value is set to 1 (white) or 0 (black) depending on whether the pixel value is greater than or equal to 255. Figure IX shows that the grayscale image is transformed into a bi-level image.

Figure IX: Transformation of Grayscale to Bi-Level Image

The “im2bw” method is employed to convert images into binary format via thresholding. Initially, it adjusts the input image to grayscale if required, followed by converting it to binary. This conversion involves assigning pixel values below a designated threshold to 0 (representing black), while those surpassing the threshold are set to 1 (representing white) [23].

3) Denoising and Smoothing:

Denoising is an essential and useful step in preprocessing for improving the quality of images for further processing like feature extraction and classification of characters. There are many methods to remove noise from the image. For Sindhi's handwritten character recognition system, filtering and morphological techniques are used. In the filtering technique, we have used the “wiener2” method and in the morphological technique, we have used the “imdilate” method. Figure X shows the noise removed from the handwritten Sindhi character.

For each pixel in the input image, “imdilate” checks the neighborhood defined by the structuring element. If any of the pixels in the neighborhood are 'on' (for binary images) or have non-zero intensity (for grayscale images), the corresponding pixel in the output image is set to 'on' or assigned a higher intensity value, effectively expanding the object or region [24].

Figure X: Removal of Noise Using Wiener 2 and Imdilate Method

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, a new dataset for "OHSCR" Offline Handwritten Sindhi Character Recognition is presented. There is no such standard publically available dataset to fill the gap in the literature for a new handwriting recognition dataset. This paper's main goal is to collect a huge dataset of handwritten characters from several writers. A total of 7800 handwritten character images were obtained from 150 male and female native writers. The noise was removed from these scanned images to create a clean dataset. The dataset created as a result of this research is the world's first publicly available dataset for handwritten research, and it can be applicable to writer identification and handwriting recognition systems. Looking ahead, there are several suggestions to make the most of the Sindhi OHSCR dataset for different OCR applications. Firstly, we should expand the dataset to 100,000 images, with 85,000 for training and 15,000 for testing, covering a variety of classes. Next, trying out different image preprocessing methods can help improve image quality. Also, we need to work on making feature extraction more efficient. Lastly, experimenting with different machine learning methods can help boost accuracy. By following these steps, we can better utilize the Sindhi OHSCR dataset for tasks like language identification, reading bank cheques, processing postal addresses, handling forms, and verifying signatures in OCR applications.

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Authors Contributions

All the authors equally contributed to this work.

Conflict of Interest

The authors affirm that this work is unique and has not been copied from any other source, including print or electronic media, and they certify that they have no competing

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Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

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